

Supplementary material to Population-based study of rare coding variants in *NR5A1/SF-1*

Table S1: Descriptions of traits assessed

Trait	Trait Processing
Age at menarche (AAM)	<p>Age at menarche (AAM) was derived from individuals in the UK Biobank (field 2714). For individuals with missing data at each recorded instance, data from the next recorded instance was used if available. Individuals reporting uncharacteristically late or early menarche (<8yo or >19yo) were collated and for them data from other instances was preferentially used if falling within the 8-19 years range.¹</p>
Age at natural menopause (ANM)	<p>In the UK Biobank, ANM was derived from participants who were deemed to have undergone natural menopause, i.e. not affected by surgical or pharmaceutical interventions, as follows: Firstly, European female participants (n=245,820) who indicated during any of the attended visits having had a hysterectomy were collated (fields 3591 and 2724) and their reported hysterectomy ages were extracted (field 2824) and the median age was kept (n=47,218 and 46,260 with reported ages). The same procedure was followed for participants indicating having undergone a bilateral oophorectomy (surgery field 2834 and age field 3882, n=20,495 and 20,001 with reported ages). For individuals having indicated the use of hormone replacement therapy (HRT; field 2814), HRT start, and end ages were collated (fields 3536 and 3546, accordingly) across the different attended visits (n=98,104). In cases where the reported chronological HRT age at later attended visits was greater than that at previous visits, the later instances were prioritized, i.e. as they would potentially indicate an updated use of HRT. In cases where different HRT ages were reported, but not in chronologically increasing order, the median age was kept. Menopausal status was determined using data across instances (field 2724) and prioritizing the latest reported data, to account for changes in menopause status. For participants indicating having undergone menopause, their reported ages at menopause were collated (field 3581) using the same procedure as for HRT ages (n=158,264). Exclusions were then applied to this age at menopause, as follows:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participants reporting undergoing a hysterectomy and/or oophorectomy, but not the age at which this happened (n=958 and 494, accordingly) • Participants reporting multiple hysterectomy and/or oophorectomy ages, which were more than 10 years apart (n=38 and 23, accordingly) • Participants reporting multiple HRT start and/or end ages, which were not in chronologically ascending order and were more than 10 years apart (n=124 and 137, accordingly) • Participants reporting multiple ages at menopause, which were not in chronologically ascending order and were more than 10 years apart (n=73) and participants who reported both having and not having been through menopause and no other interventions (n=98) • Participants having undergone a hysterectomy/oophorectomy before or during the year they report undergoing menopause • Participants starting HRT prior to undergoing menopause and participants reporting HRT use, with no accompanying dates <p>The resulting trait was representative of an age at natural menopause (ANM, n=115,051) and was used in downstream analyses.²</p>
Age at voice breaking (AVB)	<p>AVB was obtained from individuals within the UK Biobank by responses to the touchscreen question ‘When did your voice break?’ (N=191,235 men - field 2385). Participants were required to choose from one of five possible options (younger than average, about average, older than average, do not know,</p>

	prefer not to answer). Normal pubertal timing was defined in men as AVB at an “about average age”. Respondents who answered either ‘older than average’ or ‘younger than average’ were compared separately using the ‘about average’ group as a reference in a case-control design. ¹
Birth weight (Own)	Birth weight was available from individuals in the UK Biobank with available data on early life factors during verbal interview (field 20022), excluding multiple births and birth weight more than 7 kg or less than 1 kg. Birth weight of first child was derived from female individuals in the UK Biobank by responses to the touchscreen question (field 2744). ³
Blood pressure (diastolic and systolic)	Diastolic blood pressure was derived from individuals within the UK Biobank (field 4079). The average blood pressure at each assessment visit was calculated over the two available measurements and data from subsequent visits were used, if missing for a given instance. Individuals indicating the use of blood pressure medications in fields 6153 and 6177 were adjusted for in the association models. Systolic blood pressure was derived from individuals within the UK Biobank (field 4080). The average blood pressure at each assessment visit was calculated over the two available measurements and data from subsequent visits were used, if missing for a given instance. Individuals indicating the use of blood pressure medications in fields 6153 and 6177 were adjusted for in the association models. ³
Body fat percentage	Body fat percentage was derived from individuals within the UK Biobank (field 23099). ³
Body mass index (BMI)	BMI was derived from individuals within the UK Biobank with available data on body size measures (field 21001). Raw values used for all analyses after excluding individuals with missing data. ⁴
Childlessness	Childlessness was derived from the number of live births for females (field 2734) and males (field 2405) by defining individuals with no children as cases and individuals with children as controls.
Circulating IGF-1 levels	Circulating IGF-1 levels were derived from individuals in UK Biobank with available data on blood biochemistry. Individuals with > 5 SDs from the mean or individuals missing data were set to NA. ⁵
Glucose	Glucose levels were derived from individuals in UK Biobank (field 30740). Individuals with >5 SDs from the mean excluded, adjusted for cholesterol, blood pressure and diabetes medication use (fields 6153 and 6177). If first instance was missing, used second instance and accompanying medication use information. ⁵
Glycated haemoglobin (HbA1c)	Glycated haemoglobin (HbA1c) was available from individuals in the UK Biobank with available blood biochemistry data (field 30750), across instances 0 and 1, >5 SDs from mean excluded, to be adjusted for adjusted for cholesterol, blood pressure and diabetes medication use (fields 6153 and 6177). If first instance was missing, used second instance and accompanying medication use information. ⁵
HDL (high-density lipoprotein) cholesterol	HDL cholesterol was available from individuals in the UK Biobank with available blood biochemistry data (field 23406), across instances 0 and 1, >5 SDs from mean excluded, to be adjusted for cholesterol, blood pressure and diabetes medication use (fields 6153 and 6177). If first instance was missing, used second instance and accompanying medication use information. ⁵
Height	Height was derived from individuals within the UK Biobank with available data on body size measures (field 12144), excluding individuals with >4 SDs from the mean.
LDL (low-density lipoprotein) cholesterol	LDL cholesterol was available from individuals in the UK Biobank with available blood biochemistry data (field 23405), across instances 0 and 1, >5 SDs from mean excluded, to be adjusted for cholesterol, blood pressure and diabetes medication use (fields 6153 and 6177). If first instance was missing, used second instance and accompanying medication use information. ⁵
Number of live births for females	Number of live births for females was derived from individuals within the UK Biobank based on their responses to the touchscreen question, excluding individuals with more than seven children (field 2734).
Number of live births males (Children fathered)	Number of live births for males was derived from individuals within the UK Biobank based on their responses to the touchscreen question, excluding individuals with more than seven children (field 2405).
Obesity	Individuals with BMI>=30

Platelet count	Platelet count was derived from individuals in UK Biobank (field 30080). Individuals with missing data were set to NA.
Red blood cell count	Red blood cell count was derived from individuals in UK Biobank (field 30010). Individuals with >4 SDs from the mean excluded.
Relative adiposity in childhood	Comparative height at age 10 was recoded to have individuals who were in the field 1697 reported being 'Shorter' as 0, 'About average' as 1, and 'Taller' as 2. Individuals who reported 'Do not know' or 'Prefer not to answer' were set to 'NA'. Following variable recoding, this phenotype was run as a continuous trait. Comparative size at age 10, as above using data from field 1687.
Reticulocyte count	Reticulocyte count was derived from individuals in UK Biobank (field 30250). Individuals with missing data were set to NA.
SHBG (sex hormone binding globulin)	SHBG levels was derived from individuals in UK Biobank based on available data (field 30830) and adjusted: Natural Log transformed, individuals on hormone altering medication are dropped
Spleen volume	Spleen volume was derived from individuals in UK Biobank (field 21083). Individuals with missing data were set to NA.
Testosterone	Combined variable based on available data in UK Biobank (field 30850) and adjusted: For men inverse normal transformation of the residuals of a regression model including age. For women inverse normal transformation of the residuals of a regression model including age, menopausal status and operation.
Triglycerides	Triglycerides levels were derived from individuals in UK Biobank (field 30870). Individuals with >5 SDs from the mean excluded, to be adjusted for cholesterol, blood pressure and diabetes medication use (fields 6153 and 6177). If first instance was missing, used second instance and accompanying medication use information. ⁵
Type 2 diabetes	Type 2 diabetes as described in Gardner et al., 2022: In the UK Biobank, participants classified as being likely to have prevalent diabetes if they reported at either the touchscreen or nurse interview to a) have diabetes of any type other than gestational diabetes only, b) take diabetes medication, or c) had evidence from hospital episode statistics (HES) or death records data of ICD10 codes E10-E14 with a date earlier than their UKBB recruitment (5). Among those, prevalent type 2 diabetes (possible or probable) was defined according to Eastwood et al. 2016, or evidence from HES or death records data indicative of type 2 diabetes (T2D) based on ICD10 code E11 without mention of E10, or E14 without mention of E10-E13. Participants without evidence of diabetes at baseline and with evidence of ICD10 codes indicative of T2D in HES or death records data with the earliest date occurring after baseline, were classified as being likely to have incident type 2 diabetes. Participants with prevalent or incident T2D were used as T2D cases. ⁵
Waist hip ratio (WHR)	Waist hip ratio was calculated from individuals within the UK Biobank with available data on waist circumference (field 48) and hip circumference (49) and adjusted for BMI (field 21001). Individuals with >4 SDs from the mean excluded following initial calculation and prior to adjusting with BMI. Paired BMI and waist hip ration data from subsequent visits were used, if missing for a given instance.

SDs, standard deviations

Table S2: BOLT-LMM NR5A1 /SF-1 - gene level association results

Trait	MASK	MAF	AC	p value	BETA	SE
Age at natural menopause (ANM)	Missense variants with CADD \geq 25	< 0,1%	230	0,12	-0,16	0,10
Age at voice breaking (AVB)	Missense variants with CADD \geq 25	< 0,1%	225	0,26	0,02	0,02
Birth weight (Own)	Missense variants with CADD \geq 25	< 0,1%	242	0,37	0,04	0,04
BMI female	Missense variants with CADD \geq 25	< 0,1%	236	0,37	0,28	0,31
BMI male	Missense variants with CADD \geq 25	< 0,1%	236	0,6	0,14	0,26
Body fat percentage	Missense variants with CADD \geq 25	< 0,1%	467	0,17	0,37	0,27
Body mass index (BMI)	Missense variants with CADD \geq 25	< 0,1%	472	0,26	0,23	0,20
Childlessness	Missense variants with CADD \geq 25	< 0,1%	472	0,81	0,00	0,02
Childlessness female	Missense variants with CADD \geq 25	< 0,1%	236	0,43	0,02	0,02
Childlessness male	Missense variants with CADD \geq 25	< 0,1%	236	0,66	-0,01	0,03
Circulating IGF-1 levels	Missense variants with CADD \geq 25	< 0,1%	414	0,05	-0,48	0,24
Diastolic blood pressure	Missense variants with CADD \geq 25	< 0,1%	442	0,68	-0,33	0,80
Glucose	Missense variants with CADD \geq 25	< 0,1%	417	0,5	-0,03	0,04
Glycated haemoglobin (HbA1c)	Missense variants with CADD \geq 25	< 0,1%	451	0,013	0,54	0,22
HDL (high-density lipoprotein) cholesterol	Missense variants with CADD \geq 25	< 0,1%	395	0,0065	0,04	0,02
Height	Missense variants with CADD \geq 25	< 0,1%	472	0,15	-0,32	0,23
LDL (low-density lipoprotein) cholesterol	Missense variants with CADD \geq 25	< 0,1%	453	0,11	0,06	0,04
Menopause	Missense variants with CADD \geq 25	< 0,1%	131	2,6E-06	-1,76	0,38
Number of live births for females	Missense variants with CADD \geq 25	< 0,1%	236	0,11	-0,12	0,07
Number of live births males	Missense variants with CADD \geq 25	< 0,1%	236	0,62	0,04	0,08
Obesity	Missense variants with CADD \geq 25	< 0,1%	472	0,046	0,04	0,02
Red blood cell count	Missense variants with CADD \geq 25	< 0,1%	459	0,21	-0,02	0,01
Relative adiposity in childhood (SAC)	Missense variants with CADD \geq 25	< 0,1%	465	0,66	0,01	0,03
SHBG (sex hormone binding globulin)	Missense variants with CADD \geq 25	< 0,1%	386	0,054	0,04	0,02
SHBG female	Missense variants with CADD \geq 25	< 0,1%	182	0,33	0,03	0,03
SHBG male	Missense variants with CADD \geq 25	< 0,1%	204	0,075	0,05	0,03
Systolic blood pressure	Missense variants with CADD \geq 25	< 0,1%	442	0,03	0,46	0,95
Testosterone	Missense variants with CADD \geq 25	< 0,1%	433	0,45	0,04	0,05
Testosterone female	Missense variants with CADD \geq 25	< 0,1%	212	0,72	-0,02	0,07
Testosterone male	Missense variants with CADD \geq 25	< 0,1%	221	0,055	0,122	0,063
Triglycerides	Missense variants with CADD \geq 25	< 0,1%	452	0,45	-0,03	0,04
Type 2 diabetes	Missense variants with CADD \geq 25	< 0,1%	471	0,72	-0,004	0,012
Waist hip ratio (WHR)	Missense variants with CADD \geq 25	< 0,1%	472	0,29	-0,003	0,003

AC, Allele count; MAF, Minor allele frequency, SE, Standard error

Table S3: Summary of rare missense deleterious NR5A1/SF-1 variants with CADD score ≥ 25

varID	c. (HGVS)	p. (HGVS)	Functional studies	Previously reported phenotype	SF1 DOMAIN	REF	ALT	CSQ	gnomAD	CADD	REVEL	SIFT	POLYPHEN	MAF
9:124482768:T:A	c.1376A>T	K459M p.(Lys459Met)	ND	ND	LBD	T	A	missense	0	31	0,803	D	probably damaging	2,41E-06
9:124482771:G:A	c.1373C>T	A458V p.(Ala458Val)	ND	ND	LBD	G	A	missense	0	28,8	0,641	D	possibly damaging	3,30E-06
9:124482781:T:C	c.1363A>G	M455V p.(Met455Val)	ND	ND	LBD	T	C	missense	0	26,2	0,939	D	possibly damaging	1,10E-06
9:124482799:T:C	c.1345A>G	N449D p.(Asn449Asp)	ND	ND	LBD	T	C	missense	0	29,2	0,75	D	probably damaging	4,40E-06
9:124482804:G:A	c.1340C>T	P447L p.(Pro447Leu)	ND	ND	LBD	G	A	missense	0	31	0,862	D	probably damaging	2,20E-06
9:124482864:C:G	c.1280G>C	R427P p.(Arg427Pro)	ND	ND	LBD	C	G	missense	0	29,6	0,976	D	probably damaging	1,10E-06
9:124482864:C:T	c.1280G>A	R427Q p.(Arg427Gln)	ND	ND	LBD	C	T	missense	4,65E-05	29,3	0,899	D	probably damaging	2,86E-05
9:124482946:C:T	c.1198G>A	A400T p.(Ala400Thr)	Transactivation studies no impaired activity, atypical structure of protein (in silico)	Woman (31 years) with secondary amenorrhea	LBD	C	T	missense	0	25	0,882	D	probably damaging	2,20E-06
9:124482960:T:C	c.1184A>G	E395G p.(Glu395Gly)	ND	ND	LBD	T	C	missense	0	32	0,958	D	probably damaging	4,40E-06
9:124491085:G:C	c.1134C>G	S378R p.(Ser378Arg)	ND	ND	LBD	G	C	missense	0	27,9	0,868	D	possibly damaging	1,10E-06
9:124491126:G:A	c.1093C>T	R365W p.(Arg365Trp)	ND	ND	LBD	G	A	missense	0	29,8	0,881	D	probably damaging	1,43E-05
9:124491156:C:T	c.1063G>A	V355M p.(Val355Met)	Transactivation studies impaired activity, atypical structure of protein (in silico) (PMID: 17940071)	Boy with bilateral anorchia, micropenis and progressive testicular degeneration. Mother with two spontaneous miscarriages, left ovariectomy and removal of the corresponding fallopian tube due to ovarian cysts at the age of 22 (PMID: 30067310)	LBD	C	T	missense	0,00012	25,7	0,816	D	probably damaging	0,00015
9:124491167:G:A	c.1052C>T	A351V p.(Ala351Val)	ND	ND	LBD	G	A	missense	6,19E-05	26,6	0,727	D	possibly damaging	2,53E-05
9:124491189:G:C	c.1030C>G	L344V p.(Leu344Val)	ND	ND	LBD	G	C	missense	0	26,1	0,72	D	possibly damaging	5,50E-06

9:124491189:G:T	c.1030C>A	L344M p.(Leu344Met)	ND	ND	LBD	G	T	missense	0	27,3	0,826	D	probably damaging	4,40E-06
9:124493034:T:C	c.986A>G	Q329R p.(Gln329Arg)	ND	ND	LBD	T	C	missense	0	26,9	0,767	D	benign	1,10E-06
9:124493043:A:G	c.977T>C	V326A p.(Val326Ala)	Transactivation studies no impaired activity (PMID: 38623954)	Primary ovarian insufficiency (PMID: 38168586)	LBD	A	G	missense	0	31	0,752	D	probably damaging	1,10E-06
9:124493095:C:T	c.925G>A	D309N p.(Asp309Asn)	Transactivation studies no impaired activity (PMID: 38623954)	46,XY DSD (PMID: 38168586)	LBD	C	T	missense	0	29,8	0,846	D	probably damaging	3,30E-06
9:124493110:C:T	c.910G>A	E304K p.(Glu304Lys)	Transactivation studies impaired activity (PMID: 25502990)	Isolated severe hypospadias (PMID: 25502990)	LBD	C	T	missense	0	29,4	0,947	D	probably damaging	2,20E-06
9:124493143:C:T	c.877G>A	D293N p.(Asp293Asn)	Transactivation studies activity (80%) (PMID: 19246354), (100%) (PMID: 32738419), atypical protein structure (<i>in silico</i>) (PMID: 32738419)	Primary amenorrhea and signs of virilization (PMID: 19246354) 46,XY DSD (PMID: 32738419)	LBD	C	T	missense	0	26,2	0,942	D	probably damaging possibly damaging	5,50E-06
9:124500101:T:C	c.859A>G	K287E p.(Lys287Glu)	ND	ND	LBD	T	C	missense	0	28,1	0,833	D	probably damaging	1,10E-06
9:124500152:C:T	c.808G>A	D270N p.(Asp270Asn)	Transactivation studies impaired activity (PMID: 25989977)	Male (36 years old) with azoospermia and history of unilateral cryptorchidism (PMID: 25989977)	LBD	C	T	missense	0	27,7	0,764	D	probably damaging possibly damaging	1,10E-06
9:124500232:C:A	c.728G>T	R243L p.(Arg243Leu)	ND	ND	LBD	C	A	missense	0	25,5	0,544	D	probably damaging possibly damaging	1,10E-06
9:124500232:C:T	c.728G>A	R243H p.(Arg243His)	ND	ND	LBD	C	T	missense	1,55E-05	26,3	0,634	D	probably damaging probably damaging	3,30E-06
9:124500233:G:A	c.727C>T	R243C p.(Arg243Cys)	ND	ND	LBD	G	A	missense	4,65E-05	29,1	0,711	D	probably damaging probably damaging	2,53E-05
9:124500239:G:A	c.721C>T	R241W p.(Arg241Trp)	ND	46,XY sex reversal (PMID: 29095814)	LBD	G	A	missense	0	29,1	0,609	D	probably damaging	2,20E-06
9:124500256:G:A	c.704C>T	P235L p.(Pro235Leu)	Transactivation studies activity (80%), atypical protein structure (<i>in silico</i>) (PMID: 22549935)	Primary ovarian insufficiency (PMID: 22549935)	LBD	G	A	missense	1,55E-05	28,7	0,917	D	probably damaging	2,20E-05
9:124500274:T:C	c.686A>G	Q229R p.(Gln229Arg)	ND	ND	LBD	T	C	missense	1,55E-05	25,4	0,426	D	benign probably damaging	8,80E-06
9:124500298:G:T	c.662C>A	P221H p.(Pro221His)	ND	ND	HR	G	T	missense	0	25,6	0,754	D	probably damaging	1,10E-06
9:124500367:G:A	c.593C>T	P198L p.(Pro198Leu)	Transactivation studies no impaired activity (PMID: 23543655)	Woman 33y, secondary amenorrhea (PMID: 23543655)	HR	G	A	missense	0,00017	25,9	0,711	D	probably damaging	9,46E-05
9:124500389:G:A	c.571C>T	R191C p.(Arg191Cys)	Transactivation studies impaired activity (PMID: 20887963)	Spermatogenic failure and low sperm count (PMID: 20887963)	HR	G	A	missense	0	28,1	0,837	D	probably damaging possibly damaging	9,90E-06
9:124500670:G:A	c.290C>T	P97L p.(Pro97Leu)	ND	ND	DBD	G	A	missense	0	28,2	0,67	D	probably damaging	3,30E-06
9:124500674:C:T	c.286G>A	G96R p.(Gly96Arg)	ND	ND	DBD	C	T	missense	0	27,8	0,801	D	probably	4,40E-06

9:124500701:G:A	c.259C>T	R87C p.(Arg87Cys)	ND	46,XY DSD (PMID: 30425642)	DBD	G	A	missense	0	32	0,865	D	damaging probably	2,20E-06
9:124503088:G:C	c.235C>G	R79G p.(Arg79Gly)	ND	ND	DBD	G	C	missense	0	32	0,894	D	damaging possibly	1,10E-06
9:124503110:C:G	c.213G>C	Q71H p.(Gln71His)	ND	ND	DBD	C	G	missense	0	25,2	0,898	D	damaging probably	2,31E-05
9:124503341:T:C	c.55A>G	K19E p.(Lys19Glu)	ND	ND	DBD	T	C	missense	4,65E-05	25,4	0,766	D	benign	5,17E-05
			Transactivation studies impaired activity, localization assay subnuclear foci, atypical protein structure (<i>in silico</i>) (PMID: 30067310) Transactivation studies impaired activity, localization assay extranuclear foci, Electrophoretic Mobility-Shift Assay impaired activity (<i>Cyp11a</i>) (PMID: 17200175) Transactivation studies impaired activity, localization assay subnuclear foci, atypical protein structure (<i>in silico</i>) (PMID: 31787151)											
9:124503353:C:T	c.43G>A	K459M p.(Lys459Met)		46,XY sex reversal (PMID: 17200175) Primary ovarian insufficiency (PMID: 31787151)	DBD	C	T	missense	0	26,2	0,917	D	probably damaging	1,10E-06

DBD, DNA binding domain; DSD, Differences of sex development, D, deleterious; CSQ, consequence; HR, Hinge region; LBD, Ligand binding domain; *NR5A1* (ENST00000373588.49), MAF, Minor allele frequency

Table S4: BOLT-LMM NR5A1/SF-1 - variant level association results for ANM

varID	SF1 DOMAIN	AF	AC	CSQ	gnomAD	CADD	REVEL	SIFT	POLYPHEN	MAF	MAC	BOLT MAF	P LINRE				BOLT			mod.p	
													G	BETA	SE	CHISQ	B	P	BOLT		LMM
9:124482768:T:A	LBD	2,41E-06	2	missense	0	31	0,803	D	probably damaging	2,41E-06	2	5,14E-06	0,89	1,62655	4,35857	0,102841	0,75	1	1544	0,148742	FALSE
9:124482771:G:A	LBD	3,30E-06	3	missense	0	28,8	0,641	D	possibly damaging	3,30E-06	3	4,67E-06	0,98	-0,31723	4,35857	0,000905	0,98	1	1547	0,026872	TRUE
9:124482781:T:C	LBD	1,10E-06	1	missense	0	26,2	0,939	D	possibly damaging	1,10E-06	1	4,69E-06	0,7	-1,68701	4,35845	0,152943	0,7	1	1557	0,154902	TRUE
9:124482799:T:C	LBD	4,40E-06	4	missense	0	29,2	0,75	D	probably damaging	4,40E-06	4	9,35E-06	0,37	-2,23612	3,08201	0,757076	0,38	2	1575	0,327902	TRUE
9:124482804:G:A	LBD	2,20E-06	2	missense	0	31	0,862	D	probably damaging	2,20E-06	2	9,35E-06	1	-0,26555	3,08192	0,047941	0,83	2	1580	0,031517	TRUE
9:124482864:C:G	LBD	1,10E-06	1	missense	0	29,6	0,976	D	probably damaging	1,10E-06	1	4,67E-06	0,6	-20,6966	4,35855	22,8886	1,70E-06	1	1640	5,69897	TRUE
9:124482864:C:T	LBD	2,86E-05	26	missense	4,65E-05	29,3	0,899	D	probably damaging(0	2,86E-05	26	2,34E-05	0,24	-2,8008	1,94922	2,56865	0,11	5	1640	0,823909	TRUE
9:124482946:C:T	LBD	2,20E-06	2	missense	0	25	0,882	D	probably damaging	2,20E-06	2	4,67E-06	0,93	-1,43491	4,35853	0,085357	0,77	1	1722	0,130768	TRUE
9:124482960:T:C	LBD	4,40E-06	4	missense	0	32	0,958	D	probably damaging	4,40E-06	4	4,67E-06	0,61	3,31239	4,35846	0,718597	0,4	1	1736	0,346787	FALSE
9:124491085:G:C	LBD	1,10E-06	1	missense	0	27,9	0,868	D	possibly damaging	1,10E-06	1	4,67E-06	0,9	0,960117	4,35878	0,075174	0,78	1	1807	0,080922	FALSE
9:124491126:G:A	LBD	1,43E-05	13	missense	0	29,8	0,881	D	probably damaging	1,43E-05	13	1,87E-05	0,6	-0,80683	2,1793	0,007765	0,93	4	1848	0,148742	TRUE
9:124491156:C:T	LBD	0,000148	135	missense	0,000124	25,7	0,816	D	probably damaging	0,000148	135	0,000136	0,031	-1,86669	0,809485	7,24025	0,0071	29	1878	1,677781	TRUE
9:124491167:G:A	LBD	2,53E-05	23	missense	6,19E-05	26,6	0,727	D	possibly damaging	2,53E-05	23	1,87E-05	0,76	-0,51477	2,17928	0,102608	0,75	4	1889	0,091515	TRUE
9:124491189:G:C	LBD	5,50E-06	5	missense	0	26,1	0,72	D	probably damaging.	5,50E-06	5	1,40E-05	0,52	1,10663	2,5165	0,562957	0,45	3	1911	0,180456	FALSE
9:124491189:G:T	LBD	4,40E-06	4	missense	0	27,3	0,826	D	probably damaging	4,40E-06	4	9,35E-06	0,68	1,11126	3,08201	0,546836	0,46	2	1911	0,142668	FALSE
9:124493034:T:C	LBD	1,10E-06	1	missense	0	26,9	0,767	D	probably benign	1,10E-06	1	4,67E-06	0,96	-1,50101	4,35851	0,000316	0,99	1	1976	0,136677	TRUE
9:124493043:A:G	LBD	1,10E-06	1	missense	0	31	0,752	D	probably damaging	1,10E-06	1	4,67E-06	0,86	2,15935	4,35849	0,162937	0,69	1	1985	0,207608	FALSE
9:124493095:C:T	LBD	3,30E-06	3	missense	0	29,8	0,846	D	probably damaging	3,30E-06	3	4,67E-06	0,58	-1,98751	4,35857	0,350509	0,55	1	2037	0,187087	TRUE
9:124493110:C:T	LBD	2,20E-06	2	missense	0	29,4	0,947	D	probably damaging	2,20E-06	2	4,67E-06	0,84	-0,12305	4,35849	0,146909	0,7	1	2052	0,008774	TRUE
9:124493143:C:T	LBD	5,50E-06	5	missense	0	26,2	0,942	D	probably damaging	5,50E-06	5	4,67E-06	0,064	-7,39403	4,35856	2,74295	0,098	1	2085	1,045757	TRUE

9:124500101:T:C	LBD	1,10E-06	1	missense	0	28,1	0,833	D	damaging possibly	1,10E-06	1	4,67E-06	0,92	-0,40435	4,35851	0,004979	0,94	1	2124	0,031517	TRUE
9:124500152:C:T	LBD	1,10E-06	1	missense	0	27,7	0,764	D	damaging probably	1,10E-06	1	4,67E-06	0,77	-1,14318	4,35863	0,036206	0,85	1	2175	0,102373	TRUE
9:124500232:C:A	LBD	1,10E-06	1	missense	0	25,5	0,544	D	damaging possibly	1,10E-06	1	4,67E-06	0,61	2,18341	4,35844	0,122882	0,73	1	2255	0,207608	FALSE
9:124500232:C:T	LBD	3,30E-06	3	missense	1,55E-05	26,3	0,634	D	damaging. probably	3,30E-06	3	4,67E-06	0,025	-9,20098	4,35858	5,27279	0,022	1	2255	1,455932	TRUE
9:124500233:G:A	LBD	2,53E-05	23	missense	4,65E-05	29,1	0,711	D	damaging probably	2,53E-05	23	2,80E-05	0,36	-0,93738	1,77942	0,833303	0,36	6	2256	0,221849	TRUE
9:124500239:G:A	LBD	2,20E-06	2	missense	0	29,1	0,609	D	damaging probably	2,20E-06	2	9,35E-06	2	-7,25066	3,08201	4,89797	0,027	2	2262	1,721246	TRUE
9:124500256:G:A	LBD	2,20E-05	20	missense	1,55E-05	28,7	0,917	D	damaging	2,20E-05	20	1,87E-05	0,33	-1,87233	2,17933	1,16315	0,28	4	2279	0,408935	TRUE
9:124500274:T:C	LBD	8,80E-06	8	missense	1,55E-05	25,4	0,426	D	benign probably	8,80E-06	8	4,67E-06	0,63	-2,37721	4,35865	0,432666	0,51	1	2297	0,229148	TRUE
9:124500298:G:T	HR	1,10E-06	1	missense	0	25,6	0,754	D	damaging probably	1,10E-06	1	4,67E-06	0,14	6,15279	4,35873	1,52018	0,22	1	2321	0,79588	FALSE
9:124500367:G:A	HR	9,46E-05	86	missense	0,00017	25,9	0,711	D	damaging probably	9,46E-05	86	7,95E-05	0,92	-0,19286	1,05725	0,00465	0,95	17	2390	0,065502	TRUE
9:124500389:G:A	HR	9,90E-06	9	missense	0	28,1	0,837	D	damaging possibly	9,90E-06	9	2,80E-05	0,32	2,01025	1,77939	1,15622	0,28	6	2412	0,585027	FALSE
9:124500670:G:A	DBD	3,30E-06	3	missense	0	28,2	0,67	D	damaging probably	3,30E-06	3	4,67E-06	0,53	-1,58086	4,3585	0,214498	0,64	1	2693	0,142668	TRUE
9:124500674:C:T	DBD	4,40E-06	4	missense	0	27,8	0,801	D	damaging probably	4,40E-06	4	4,67E-06	0,53	-2,51862	4,35868	0,19108	0,66	1	2697	0,251812	TRUE
9:124500701:G:A	DBD	2,20E-06	2	missense	0	32	0,865	D	damaging possibly	2,20E-06	2	4,67E-06	0,6	-2,40321	4,35862	0,222396	0,64	1	2724	0,236572	TRUE
9:124503088:G:C	DBD	1,10E-06	1	missense	0	32	0,894	D	damaging probably	1,10E-06	1	4,67E-06	0,91	-1,80751	4,35845	0,027924	0,87	1	2769	0,167491	TRUE
9:124503110:C:G	DBD	2,31E-05	21	missense	0	25,2	0,898	D	damaging	2,31E-05	21	3,74E-05	4	-5,223	1,54109	11,4719	0,00071	8	2791	3,154902	TRUE
9:124503341:T:C	DBD	5,17E-05	47	missense	4,65E-05	25,4	0,766	D	benign probably	5,17E-05	47	6,54E-05	4	-3,32787	1,16505	6,82385	0,009	14	2970	2,366532	TRUE
9:124503353:C:T	DBD	1,10E-06	1	missense	0	26,2	0,917	D	damaging	1,10E-06	1	4,67E-06	0,043	-10,0945	4,35844	6,09707	0,014	1	2982	1,677781	TRUE

AF, allele frequency; AC, allele count, DBD, DNA binding domain; DSD, Differences of sex development, D, deleterious; CSQ, consequence; HR, Hinge region; LBD, Ligand binding domain; NR5A1 (ENST00000373588.49), MAC, minor allele count; MAF, minor allele frequency

Table S5: GLM *NR5A1/SF-1* - gene level association results. Rare missense variants (MAF < 0.1%) with CADD \geq 25 in LBD or DBD domains

Trait	BETA	SE	p value	Number of carriers
Age at natural menopause (ANM)	-2,36	0,43	4,6E-08	107
Age at menarche	-0,20	0,12	1,1E-01	171
Age at voice breaking (AVB)	0,02	0,02	5,2E-01	160
Birth weight (Own)	0,06	0,05	2,1E-01	179
BMI female	0,75	0,38	5,1E-02	176
BMI male	0,13	0,32	7,0E-01	168
Body fat percentage	0,54	0,34	1,1E-01	342
Body mass index (BMI)	0,44	0,25	8,4E-02	344
Childlessness female	0,01	0,03	8,6E-01	176
Childlessness male	-0,01	0,03	8,3E-01	168
Circulating IGF-1 levels	-0,39	0,30	2,0E-01	304
Diastolic blood pressure	0,77	0,97	4,3E-01	321
Glucose	-0,03	0,05	4,8E-01	304
Glycated haemoglobin (HbA1c)	0,30	0,28	2,7E-01	330
HDL (high-density lipoprotein) cholesterol	0,03	0,02	8,0E-02	305
Height	-0,52	0,34	1,2E-01	344
LDL (low-density lipoprotein) cholesterol	0,02	0,05	7,4E-01	332
Number of live births for females	-0,10	0,09	2,3E-01	176
Number of live births for males	-0,002	0,092	9,8E-01	168
Obesity	0,06	0,02	1,5E-02	344
Obesity female	0,09	0,03	3,9E-03	176
Obesity male	0,02	0,03	5,7E-01	168
Platelet count	8,55	3,16	6,8E-03	334
Red blood cells count	-0,02	0,02	3,8E-01	336
Relative adiposity in childhood (SAC)	0,02	0,04	6,6E-01	339
Reticulocyte count	-0,01	0,01	2,9E-01	17
SHBG female	0,02	0,08	7,8E-01	158
SHBG male	0,14	0,08	7,7E-02	160
Spleen volume	-0,01	0,01	5,1E-01	29
Systolic blood pressure	0,86	0,55	1,2E-01	321
Testosterone female	0,02	0,08	7,8E-01	158
Testosterone male	0,14	0,08	7,7E-02	160
Triglycerides	-0,07	0,05	1,8E-01	331
Type 2 diabetes	-0,01	0,01	3,8E-01	343
Waist hip ratio (WHR)	-0,003	0,004	4,6E-01	344

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